

Triad of Success: Emotional Intelligence, Self-Regulated Learning, and English Proficiency of Senior High School Students

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Abstract

This study investigated the relationship between emotional intelligence, self-regulated learning, and English proficiency among senior high school students. The research employed a descriptive-correlational design and was conducted at Esperanza National High School, involving 320 senior high school students for the school year 2024–2025. A stratified sampling technique was used, with Senior High School Strands serving as the strata. Descriptive statistics, such as mean and standard deviation, were utilized to determine the levels of emotional intelligence, self-regulated learning, and English proficiency, while inferential statistics, specifically Pearson correlation, assessed the relationships between these variables. The results revealed a strong positive correlation between

emotional intelligence and English proficiency $r = 0.758$, $p < 0.001$, and a weak positive correlation between self-regulated learning and English proficiency $r = 0.282$, $p < 0.001$. Despite high levels of emotional intelligence and self-regulated learning, students demonstrated only moderate English proficiency. The study concludes that emotional intelligence plays a pivotal role in enhancing English skills, suggesting the importance of integrating emotional intelligence development into educational programs. School may develop comprehensive programs and activities aimed at enhancing emotional intelligence among students. This can include workshops, seminars, and group activities that focus on developing empathy, self-regulation, and social skills.

Keywords: *Challenges, Motivations, Quality of Life, Wealth Accumulation, Farmers*

1.0 Introduction

Imagine being in a classroom where students from different backgrounds struggle to talk to each other. This is a real problem for many students around the world today.

English is the primary language used for teaching and communication; everyone needs to show good English skills, no matter where they come from. This need is crucial to ensure that every student can achieve in their preferred course of study. Moreover, emotional intelligence helps pupils develop relationships with people and understand them more precisely qualities absolutely important in a classroom.

For many students, English competency still causes great global worry. English is the primary language of instruction in many disciplines. Hence, students have to be proficient in it if they want to flourish intellectually. Many of them sadly struggle with English speaking and writing, which might lower their confidence and negatively impact their class performance (Emirza and Sahril, 2021). Students had fewer chances to improve their language skills and participate in meaningful conversations when they switched to online learning during the pandemic, aggravating this problem (Manzini, 2023).

English is important for communication in many countries and is often necessary for academic success and future job opportunities. Unfortunately, many students do not receive enough support to improve their English skills (CHITHANURU, 2021). Another issue is the lack of research on how emotional intelligence, self-regulated learning, and English proficiency are connected. While it is known that emotional intelligence can help with academic performance, many schools focus mainly on cognitive skills instead of teaching students how to manage their emotions (Ha, 2019).

Many students worldwide struggle with emotional intelligence, which is the ability to understand and manage their feelings and the feelings of others. Research shows that emotional intelligence scores have declined, leading to difficulties in coping with stress and challenges (Brinzea, 2022). Self-regulated learning is another area where students face challenges. However, not many students can harness these skills independently, especially when faced with emotional challenges (ALABDULLATIF, 2020).

In the Philippines, a study by De Manuel (2022) revealed that students are overwhelmed and anxious during exams because of their poor emotional quotient. In addition, self-regulated learning is a significant problem; many students cannot identify their learning objectives and monitor their learning progress. This struggle is especially evident among students from low-income families who may not have the materials or assistance needed to develop good learning strategies as much as their peers, as highlighted by Ha (2019).

In Sultan Kudarat, English is the primary medium of instruction in schools; however, students there have problems with language proficiency because of the lack of exposure and practice. The absence of support for developing emotional intelligence and self-regulated learning skills worsens this problem. Research shows that stress and anxiety levels among students are usually high due to academic pressure, which affects their performance adversely (De Manuel, 2022).

Despite the importance of emotional intelligence, self-regulated learning, and English proficiency in academic success, there is a significant lack of comprehensive studies that explore how these areas intersect among senior high school students in the province. Most existing research examines these topics separately rather than considering their interconnections. Additionally, there is limited empirical data on the specific experiences and needs of students in this province, particularly those from diverse socio-economic backgrounds.

Thus, this study investigated how emotional intelligence, self-regulated learning, and English proficiency are related among senior high school students in Sultan Kudarat. Given that English is the primary language of instruction, but many students struggle with it, the study aimed to understand how being emotionally aware can help students manage their learning and improve their English skills.

2.0 Methodology

2.1 Research Design

The study utilized the descriptive-correlational research design to investigate the relationship between emotional intelligence and self-regulated learning (independent variables) and English proficiency (dependent variable) of Senior High School students. The independent variables, emotional intelligence, comprises five specific indicators: self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills

while the self-regulated learning comprises six specific indicators: self-efficacy, self-confidence, behavioral discipline, sense of responsibility, thinking on your initiatives and conducting self evaluation. The dependent variable, English proficiency, is measured through two indicators: grammar and reading comprehension. In this correlational research approach, the study will examine how the indicators of emotional intelligence and self-regulated learning potentially correlate with English proficiency among Senior High School students. By employing a descriptive-correlational method, the research will objectively analyze the natural relationships between these variables without attempting to manipulate or establish direct causation. Miksza and Elpus (2018) define descriptive research as observing behavior to describe attributes objectively and systematically. Steinberg and Lam (2011) describe correlational research as a method that predicts how variables are naturally related in the real world.

2.2 Research Locale

The study was conducted in Esperanza National High School (ENHS), Mabolo Street, Brgy. Poblacion, Esperanza, Sultan Kudarat.

2.3 Research Participants

The respondents for this study consisted of 320 Senior High School (SHS) students of Esperanza National High School, Division of Sultan Kudarat for the school year 2024 – 2025. The study focused on Senior High School students for several important reasons. First, this age group, typically between 16 and 18 years old, is at a crucial point in their lives where they are preparing for their future. They are learning essential skills that will help them in college and jobs later on. Understanding how they feel and how they learn can help them do better in school. Second, English is a very important language for students today. It is used in many subjects and is necessary for getting good jobs in the future. Unfortunately, many Senior High School students struggle with their English skills because they do not practice enough or receive the support they need at home or school (Ambayon, 2021). Lastly, many students come from families with different economic backgrounds. Some may not have the resources to help them improve their learning skills (Munir et al., 2023).

2.4 Research Instrument

This study employed three sets of adopted research instruments to gather data effectively. The first set is an adopted research survey questionnaire from the study of Hasibuan and Irwandi (2024). This questionnaire assessed the level of emotional intelligence among respondents, focusing on five key components, self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy, and social skills as identified by Goleman (1995). The second set of instruments is adopted from the study of Shaheema et al., (2023). This set evaluated the level of self-regulated learning in terms of self-efficacy, self-confidence, behavioral discipline, sense of responsibility, thinking on one's initiatives, and conducting self-evaluation. The last set consists of an English Proficiency Test adopted from the study Manuel (2022) titled English Language Proficiency of Senior High School Students. This test includes a 40-item Grammar Test covering the eight parts of speech: nouns, pronouns, verbs, adjectives, adverbs, prepositions, conjunctions, and interjections. Additionally, it features a 42-item Reading Comprehension Test that assesses understanding across three literary genres: poems, essays, and short stories. Each text in the reading comprehension section includes four sets of questions that target different levels of understanding: literal comprehension, interpretation, evaluation, and integration. Each of the research instruments were validated. Experts in the field were asked to review both sets of questionnaires. Content Validity Forms were sent to the panel of content validators for review. After tallying and averaging the responses from three (3) content validators, the Survey Questionnaires were given an overall mean score of 5.00. Please refer to the section below for a detailed explanation of how to make sense of the validation result.

2.5 Data Gathering Procedure

The researchers secured all necessary Communication Letters from the Graduate School of Sultan Kudarat State University. For the validity and reliability tests of the three (3) sets of research instruments, they asked permission from the research experts to validate the research instrument. After ensuring the research instrument's validity they requested the approval of the Schools Division Superintendent of the Division of Sultan Kudarat to administer the survey questionnaire to the Senior High School students of Esperanza National High School. An approval letter from the Office of the Schools Division Superintendent was attached to seek permission from the Principal of Esperanza National High School. After all survey questionnaires were gathered, the results were consolidated for data analysis.

2.6 Ethical Considerations

This research study followed ethical guidelines. The respondents' participation was entirely voluntary, and they could leave the study at any time if they felt uncomfortable. There was no physical, social, psychological, or any other form of harm to the respondents' participation. The dignity and well-being of teachers and students who responded were always protected. The research data remained confidential throughout the study, and the respondents' rights were protected to maintain scientific or academic integrity. In addition, this research study is plagiarism-free and without research misconduct.

3.0 Results and Discussion

3.1 Emotional Intelligence of the Students

Emotional intelligence among students refers to their ability to recognize, understand, manage, and express emotions effectively while navigating social relationships and academic challenges. The findings present the level of emotional intelligence of the respondents in terms of self-awareness, self-regulation, motivation, empathy and social skills.

Table 1. Consolidated findings of the Level of Emotional Intelligence of the Students

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
A. Self-Awareness	3.97	0.77	High
B. Self-Regulation	3.49	0.97	High
C. Motivation	3.75	0.95	High
D. Empathy	3.82	1.09	High
E. Social Skills	3.68	1.05	High
Overall Mean	3.74	0.97	High

Note: 4.21 - 5.00 *Very High*
 3.41 - 4.20 *High*
 2.61 - 3.40 *Moderately High*
 1.81 - 2.60 *Low*
 1.00 - 1.80 *Very Low*

Emotional Intelligence of the Students

Table 1 shows students' levels of emotional intelligence across several key indicators and the result shows that the mean of all the indicators is 3.74 with standard deviation of 0.97. On aggregate, students are shown to have a good level of emotional intelligence which is vital for academic achievement and growth.

In particular, empathy was rated the highest with a mean of 3.82, classified as high, and standard deviation of 1.09. This result shows that students are capable of emotional understanding and expression, which is important for group work and creating positive learning environments. Empathy also helps in communication and conflict solving as students are likely to have better relationships with their peers.

However, self regulation has the lowest mean score of 3.49, which is interpreted as high, and a standard deviation of 0.97. This means that although students are good in emotion regulation they may struggle with

consistency in various contexts. Rentzios et al. (2025) pointed out that emotional intelligence is important for learning independently and controlling emotions which, in turn, affects academic productivity. Moreover, Taheri et al. (2019) explained that emotional intelligence increases the learners' willingness, passion, and commitment in the language learning process which in turn leads to increased language proficiency. This therefore means that emotional intelligence should be encouraged in order to help students in every aspect of their academic achievement.

The findings indicate that students exhibit a strong sense of empathy, particularly in understanding others' perspectives. However, there is room for improvement in fully identifying with their peers' emotions. Research by Sierksma & Bijlstra (2018) found that when students feel understood and supported by their peers and teachers, they are more likely to participate actively in class discussions and collaborative projects.

3.2 Self-regulated Learning of the Students

Self-regulated learning is a process where learners actively take control of their own education by setting goals, managing their time and resources, monitoring their progress, and adjusting strategies as needed. It involves cognitive, motivational, and behavioral components, allowing students to take responsibility for their learning and improve performance through reflection and self-assessment.

The table pertains to the level of self-regulated learning of the respondents in terms of dependence on others or self-efficacy, self-confidence, behavioral discipline, sense of responsibility, thinking on your initiatives, and conducting self evaluation.

Table 2. Consolidated findings of the Level of Self-regulated learning of the Students

Indicators	Mean	SD	Verbal Description
A. Dependence on others	3.97	0.87	High
B. Self – Confidence	3.42	0.77	High
C. Behavioral Discipline	3.85	0.65	High
D. Sense of Responsibility	3.82	1.12	High
E. Thinking on your Initiatives	3.88	1.15	High
F. Conducting self-evaluation	3.46	1.02	High
Overall Mean	3.73	0.93	High
<i>Note:</i>	<i>4.21 - 5.00</i>	<i>Very High</i>	
	<i>3.41 - 4.20</i>	<i>High</i>	
	<i>2.61 - 3.40</i>	<i>Moderately High</i>	
	<i>1.81 - 2.60</i>	<i>Low</i>	
	<i>1.00 - 1.80</i>	<i>Very Low</i>	

Self-regulated Learning of the Students

The overall mean score for students' self-regulated learning is 3.73 with standard deviation of 0.93. This means that students on average manifest high levels of self-regulation in their learning activities, which implies that they are well placed to manage their academic responsibilities.

Among the various indicators, the highest mean score is found in Dependence on others, which had a mean of 3.97, classified as High, with a standard deviation of 0.87. This means that students are certain of their capability to work independently in learning activities, but they also realize that sometimes it is acceptable to seek help from others. Zheng (2019) stresses that self-regulated learning is a combination of autonomy and the capacity to seek support, which is a harmonious coexistence of independence and teamwork.

However, the lowest mean score was observed for self-confidence which had a mean of 3.46, interpreted as high, with a standard deviation of 1.02. This means that although students have a positive perception of their confidence, there is potential for enhancement in students' perception of their capability

to challenge and lead in learning. Maromon & Marpaung (2023) explained that self-regulated learning is a process where students learn to manage themselves in order to learn as they interact with their learning environment, therefore, building students' self-confidence is crucial for them to become more independent in learning.

The remaining indicators demonstrated high interpretations, behavioral discipline with a mean of 3.85, sense of responsibility at 3.82, thinking on your initiatives at 3.88, and conducting self-evaluation at 3.46, further supporting the notion that students are engaged in their learning processes and exhibit responsibility and discipline in their academic endeavors. Theobald (2021) asserted that self-regulated learning involves students taking charge of their educational activities independently, which aligns with these findings.

3.3 English Proficiency of the Students

Tables 3 present the level of English proficiency of the respondents in grammar and reading comprehension.

Table 3. Consolidated findings of the English proficiency of the Students

Indicators	Mean	SD	Description
A. Grammar	24.46	7.56	Moderate
B. Reading Comprehension	24.45	11.99	Moderate
Overall Mean	24.46	9.78	Moderate

English Proficiency of the Students

The overall mean score for English proficiency of the students is 24.46, which is interpreted as moderate, with a standard deviation of 9.78, as indicated in Table 14. This means that students are generally moderately proficient in English, meaning they have some basic skills that may not extend to more complex aspects of the language.

Grammar had the highest mean score of 24.46, classified as moderate, with a standard deviation of 7.56. This indicates that students have a moderate grasp of the English grammar concepts, but they may find it difficult to use complex structures correctly. Manuel (2022) pointed out that grammar is usually regarded as difficult, especially in terms of learning verbs and adverbs, which can lead to misunderstandings. Teacher-led instruction and controlled practice are recommended to help overcome recurring errors and enhance the grammatical sophistication of students' writing (Adebayo et al., 2024).

With the lowest mean score of 24.45, reading comprehension was also interpreted as moderate, with standard deviation of 11.99. It indicates that students may not be able to grasp the whole meaning of the texts, and may have problems with respectively unfamiliar vocabulary or complicated ideas.

Zunino (2021) explained that reading comprehension is a cognitive process requiring both decoding skills and the ability to connect prior knowledge with new information. The Program for International Student Assessment (PISA) 2018 also noted below-average reading literacy scores among Filipino students, emphasizing the need for targeted interventions to improve comprehension skills.

The result shows that senior high school students have a moderate English proficiency level and have a better performance in grammar than in reading comprehension. Such challenges may include; limited practice opportunities and insufficient support as noted by JAILANI (2018).

3.4 Emotional Intelligence and English Proficiency of Students

This study investigates the significant relationship between emotional intelligence and English proficiency among senior high school students, aiming to determine how emotional awareness, regulation, and interpersonal skills may influence their language learning and communication abilities as presented in Table 4.

Table 4. Correlational analysis between the Emotional Intelligence and English Proficiency of Senior High School Students

Variables	<i>r</i>	t - computed	p - value	Interpretation
Emotional Intelligence and English Proficiency of Students	0.758	79.61	0.00000	Significant

Note: ns - not significant at .05 level

Table 4 presents the relationship between emotional intelligence and English proficiency among senior high school students. The results indicate a statistically significant strong positive correlation between these two variables $r=0.758$, $t=79.61$, $p=0.00000$.

The Pearson correlation coefficient $r=0.758$ suggests a strong positive relationship. This indicates that as students' emotional intelligence increases, their English proficiency also tends to improve significantly.

The t computed value of 79.61 is statistically significant, with a p-value of 0.00000. Since the p – value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (that there is no relationship between emotional intelligence and English proficiency) is rejected. This provides a strong evidence that the observed correlation is not due to chance.

These findings indicate that emotional intelligence is a key contributor to improving English proficiency among senior high school students. Emotional intelligence, understood as the ability to understand and manage emotions, to build relationships and solve problems, might have a positive effect on language learning by decreasing anxiety and increasing motivation and engagement (Aljasir, 2024). Those students with high emotional intelligence are more likely to be able to cope with stress and to regulate their learning, thus achieving better language learning outcomes (Nurmeli and Idris, 2024).

This aligns with prior research emphasizing the importance of emotional intelligence in academic achievement, particularly in language learning contexts where emotional regulation and adaptability are essential for success (Carracedo, 2022). However, while emotional intelligence is a significant factor, it should be considered alongside other elements such as instructional quality and exposure to language practice (Hughes, 2016).

3.5 Self-regulated learning and English Proficiency of Students

Table 4 presents the significant relationship between self-regulated learning and English proficiency of Senior High School students.

Table 4. Correlational analysis between the Emotional Intelligence and English Proficiency of Senior High School Students

Variables	<i>r</i>	t - computed	p - value	Interpretation
Self-regulated Learning and English Proficiency of Students	0.282	80.28	0.00000	Significant

Note: ns - not significant at .05 level

As shown in table 4, the relationship between self-regulated learning and English proficiency among senior high school students. The results indicate a statistically significant weak positive correlation between these two variables $r=0.282$, $t=80.28$, $p=0.00000$.

The Pearson correlation coefficient $r=0.282$ suggests a weak positive relationship. This indicates that as students' self-regulated learning improves, their English proficiency shows a slight but noticeable increase. The t computed value of 80.28 is statistically significant, with a p – value of 0.00000. Since the p – value is less than the alpha level of 0.05, the null hypothesis (that there is no relationship between self-regulated learning and English proficiency) is rejected. This provides a fairly strong evidence that the observed correlation is not due to chance.

These findings emphasize the role of self-regulated learning in improving English proficiency though the effect was not as strong as that of other factors such as emotional intelligence. Self-regulated learning refers to students' active role in managing their learning processes, including setting goals, monitoring progress, and reflecting on learning (Paulina et al., 2023). As for the latter, researchers have established that students with high self-regulation abilities tend to use proper cognitive and metacognitive strategies, including planning and organizing their study schedules, which, in turn, benefits language learning (Intan Palullu and Bahri, 2023).

However, while self-regulated learning contributes to English proficiency, its effect may be limited by external factors such as instructional quality and access to resources (Bravo, 2022). Learners from resource-limited environments may struggle to fully develop self-regulation skills, impacting their ability to achieve higher language proficiency levels (Wang, 2021).

3.6 The Designed Intervention Program to Enhance the English Language Proficiency of the Senior High School Students

Based on the results of the study, there is a need to design an intervention program to enhance the English language proficiency of senior high school students due to observed gaps in their communication skills, which can affect their academic performance and future career opportunities. Many students struggle with core language areas such as grammar, vocabulary, and fluency, making it essential to implement targeted strategies that support their learning needs. An effective intervention program provides structured support, boosts confidence, and promotes active language use in both academic and real-world contexts.

Thus, in this study, an intervention program titled Enhanced English Mastery Through Emotional Intelligence and Self-Regulated Learning (EEMESRL) activity is proposed. It is a semester-long initiative designed to elevate English proficiency among senior high school students at Esperanza National High School, Sultan Kudarat. Spearheaded by the researcher and coordinated by the Senior High School Language Group.

Recent studies have highlighted the effectiveness of targeted intervention programs in addressing these issues. Bituin (2024) conducted a study focusing on the speaking skills of senior high school students, identifying pronunciation and interaction as significant areas of concern. They developed an intervention program that effectively addressed these specific challenges, leading to improved speaking proficiency among the participants. Similarly, Eslit & Valderama (2023) implemented a class intervention program focusing on grammar and fluency, which resulted in notable improvements in students' English proficiency. These findings underscore the necessity of designing and implementing intervention programs tailored to the specific needs of senior high school students to enhance their English language proficiency.

4.0 Conclusion

Students demonstrate strong empathy but face greater challenges in managing their emotions, highlighting a need to balance these skills for academic and personal growth. While students are good at managing their work and staying disciplined but struggle with self-confidence and evaluating their own learning, showing both strengths and areas to work on. Additionally, students handle grammar better than reading, showing

where to focus to strengthen their English Language Skills. Emotional intelligence and English language skills are closely linked, meaning better emotional awareness often comes with stronger language abilities. Meanwhile, the students who actively manage their learning strategies may achieve slight improvements in English language skills. Thus, the study highlights the need for a balanced development of both emotional intelligence and self-regulated learning among senior high school students to enhance their English language proficiency. Strengthening students' emotional management and independent learning strategies can lead to improved language skills, especially in areas like reading and comprehension. This calls for well-designed intervention programs that address both emotional and academic needs.

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